

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

AN INSIGHT TO A RARE GENETIC DISORDER: FATAL FAMILIAL INSOMNIA

Syeda Jabeen Fatima^{*}, Humera Sadia, Syeda Sana, Syeda Rabia Uzma, Syeda Khadija Hashmath

Department of Pharmacology, Shadan Women's College of Pharmacy, Khairtabad, Hyderabad - 500004, Telangana.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 07/07/2021

Available online

31/07/2021

Keywords

Fatal Familial Insomnia (FFI);
Prion Protein Gene (PRNP);
Neurodegenerative;
Sleep Disorder;
Motor Dysfunction;
CSF Studies.

ABSTRACT

This review study was carried out to educate people about a rare genetic disorder that is fatal familial insomnia. Fatal familial insomnia (FFI) is an autosomal dominant inherited neurodegenerative disorder caused by mutation in the prion protein gene (PRNP) at codon 178 located in the short arm of chromosome 20 at position p13 responsible for making of prion protein. The disease-causing mutation consist of substitution from normal aspartic acid (Asp) to asparagine (Asn). The presence of methionine at codon 129 is distinct for FFI compared to valine at the same position in Familial Creutzfeldt -Jakob disease. The more aggressive variant has methionine (Met-Met) on the non-mutated allele compared to variant which has valine (Met-Val) [1]. Prion related diseases are Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease [11], Kuru [12], Grestmann straussler syndrome [13]. FFI is characterized by severe sleep disorder caused by psychiatric symptoms and vegetative symptoms [1] with motor dysfunction of sleep generation mechanism has been called as "Agrypnia excitata" [13]. Both familial and sporadic FFI can be evaluated by CSF studies, PSG, electroencephalogram, molecular genetic testing, biopsy and imaging [5]. FFI is diagnosed by PRNP Gene test. There is no cure for FFI and no standardized treatment protocols. Only symptomatic treatment is centered on relief and palliative cure along with investigational therapy and current therapy is monitored by accompanying with self-management [3]. The disease course lasts from 7-36 months with an average duration of 18 months leading to eventual death [1]. The review study carried out suggests the need for future research and clinical studies in patients with the disorder.

Corresponding author

Syeda Jabeen Fatima

Assistant Professor,

Department of Pharmacology

Shadan Women's College of Pharmacy,

Khairtabad, Hyderabad - 500004, Telangana, India.

+91-9885979809, +91-6305927704

syedajabeenfatima87@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press a **Syeda Jabeen Fatima et al. An Insight to A Rare Genetic Disorder: Fatal Familial Insomnia.** *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.*2021;11(07).

Copy right © 2021 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

AIM

To study about a rare genetic disorder that is fatal familial insomnia.

OBJECTIVE

To perform a detailed study of fatal familial insomnia which is a rare disorder through review of literature and educate people about its symptoms and self-management.

INTRODUCTION TO FATAL FAMILIAL INSOMNIA

Sleep plays an important role in the function of the brain, by forming new pathways and processing information. Research has shown that adequate sleep helps to improve memory and learning, increase attention and creativity, and aid in making decisions. Nevertheless, it is quite evident that sleep is essential for many vital functions including development, energy conservation, brain waste clearance, modulation of immune responses, cognition, performance, vigilance, disease, and psychological state [2]. Without an adequate amount of sleep, one would be at risk for not only diseases, but also effects on executive functions. And some may not be able to sleep because of a serious disease such as Fatal Familial Insomnia. Fatal familial insomnia is a very rare and invariably fatal autosomal dominant neurodegenerative prion disease. FFI is universally fatal with limited treatment options currently. Therefore, it is very important for people and families to be thoroughly educated and made aware about the fatal course of FFI.

Fatal Familial Insomnia (FFI) which is a very rare disorder that runs in families. It affects the thalamus. This brain structure controls many things, including emotional expression and sleep. While the main symptom is insomnia, FFI can also cause a range of other symptoms, such as speech problems and dementia [3]. FFI gets its name partly from the fact that it often causes death within a year of two of symptoms starting. However, this timeline can vary from person to person. It's part of a family of conditions known as prion diseases. These are rare conditions that cause a loss of nerve cells in the brain [4].

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS:

The characteristic symptom of FFI is progressive insomnia. Insomnia often begins during middle age, but it can occur earlier or later in life. Insomnia may first be mild, but it then becomes progressively worse until an affected individual gets very little sleep. Insomnia usually begins suddenly and can rapidly worsen over the next few months. When sleep is achieved, vivid dreams may occur. The lack of sleep leads to physical and mental deterioration and the disease ultimately progresses to coma and death. Although insomnia is usually the first symptom, some individuals may present with progressive dementia in which there are worsening problems. Episodes of confusion and hallucinations can eventually occur [5].

CAUSES:

FFI is caused by a mutation of the PRNP gene. This mutation causes an attack on the thalamus, which controls your sleep cycles and allows different parts of your brain to communicate with each other. It's considered a progressive neurodegenerative disease. Some individuals have developed Fatal Insomnia (FI) without a variation in the PRNP gene. The PRNP produces a protein called prion protein or PrP. The exact function of PrP in the body is not fully understood. The misfolded PrP is toxic to the body, especially cells of the nervous system. As the misfolded PrP builds up in the thalamus, it results in a progressive destruction of nerve cells, which leads to the symptoms of a disorder [6].

Motor disturbances associated with sleep can be loosely sorted into two categories.

In the first category, there are motor disturbances (Diurnal Movement Disorders) present during the day time that may have an impact on sleep, either directly through their motor effects or indirectly through a variety of other mechanisms. These are the typical movement disorders that are seen by a movement disorders specialist.

In the second category, there are motor disturbances that are predominantly associated with sleep. They may be motor activity similar to what is normally found during waking hours that intrudes upon sleep or abnormal motor activity that does not occur during the wake state but is aroused by sleep. These are generally classified as sleep disorders and primarily are treated by a sleep disorder specialist [6].

EVALUATION:

If they suspect fatal familial insomnia, a doctor might use a PET scan, which records activity in the body's tissues and organs. This type of scan can detect abnormalities in the thalamus.

In some cases, a doctor may use genetic testing to check for the characteristic PRNP gene mutation. Periodic sharp-wave complexes (PSWC) can suggest prion disease but are seen in only a small percentage of patients with genetic forms of prion disease. Computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) have limited value in diagnosing FFI but may help rule out other neurological pathologies [5].

DIAGNOSIS:

If the PRNP gene test is positive FFI, a diagnosis of definitive FFI can be confirmed. The organic sleep-related abnormalities (a) in addition to one or two other core features (b/c) are essential for a diagnosis of possible FFI. Positive family history of RPD and insomnia, organic insomnia, sleep-related apnea, laryngeal stridor, and involuntary movements revealed by PSG low glucose uptake in the thalamus demonstrated by SPECT or PET imaging. FFI patients are more likely to have longer disease durations, severe insomnia and dysautonomia, and are less likely to have typical CJD-like cortical ribboning in DWI. GSS has been associated with many point mutations or insertional mutations of octapeptide repeats, and DI78N has not been identified in GSS. Limbic DWI or FLAIR hyperintensities can be found in upto 50% of cases [7].

TREATMENT:

There is no cure, but investigators are researching ways to best treat and manage FFI. There are no standardized treatment protocols or guidelines for affected individuals. Due to the rarity of the disease, there are no treatment trials that have been tested on large group of patients. Genetic counselling is recommended for affected individuals and their families. Psychological support for the entire family is essential as well. Symptomatic treatments include anti-seizure medications for seizures or clonazepam for myoclonus. Affected individuals may be advised to discontinue any medications that worsen confusion, memory or insomnia. Melatonin supplements could also be introduced in the early stages of the disease since plasmatic melatonin is drastically decreased. Melatonin is a natural endogenous molecule, therefore side effects will be less frequent [8].

INVESTIGATIONS AND CURRENT THERAPY:

Although the ultimate therapy for FFI must address the destructive prion, present treatment of FFI is mainly palliative. FFI patients respond poorly to conventional drugs such as sedatives and benzodiazepines. Cibula and colleagues mention giving a cocktail of medications to successfully induce SWS and sleep spindles for EEG testing of an insomniac, non-FFI patient without thalamic degeneration. Gamma-hydroxybutyrate (GHB), an investigational drug reliably stimulates SWS in normal and insomniac patients, resulted in 3 hours of SWS sleep in a patient with FFI of 14 months' duration (3-mg dose) [9].

SELF-MANAGEMENT:

The use of vitamins, narcoleptics, stimulation, sensory deprivation, exercise, light entrainment, and GH may offer some possibilities in patient management of FFI. Stimulant medication will provide a better quality of life, enabling the patient to overcome his or her stupor and fill the day with productive activity. However, there are treatments for specific symptoms, such as muscle spasms. People with fatal familial insomnia tend to live between 7 months and 3 years after the symptoms become apparent [9].

However, researchers are actively working toward effective treatments and preventive measures. A 2016 animal study suggests that immunotherapy may help, but additional research, including human studies, are needed. There's also an ongoing human study involving the use of doxycycline, an antibiotic. Researchers think that this may be an effective way to prevent FFI who carry the genetic mutation that causes it.

CONCLUSION

Fatal familial insomnia is best managed by an interprofessional team, including sleep specialists, neurologists, psychiatrists and psychologists, social workers, palliative nurses, and hospice care. This disorder has no cure and is managed by first making the patient comfortable and improving the quality of life. Patients and families should be thoroughly educated about the fatal course of FFI. They should also be made aware that there are limited treatment options currently, but the studies are ongoing. Genetic counselling should be offered to family members as well. Psychological counselling for family members is necessary as well. Various articles reviewed recommends the need for further research due to unavailability of standard treatment therapy.

COMPETING INTERESTS:

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

All the authors are thankful to Dr. Ramakrishna D, Principal Shadan Women's College of Pharmacy for providing necessary computational facility to carry out the research work.

ABBREVIATIONS

FFI	: Fatal Familial Insomnia
PRNP	: Prion protein gene
Asp	: Aspartic acid
Asn	: Asparagine
Val	: Valine
Met	: Methionine
CSF	: Cerebrospinal fluid
PSG	: Polysomnography
PSWC	: Periodic sharp wave complex
PET	: Positron Emission Tomography
CT	: Computed Tomography
MRI	: Magnetic Resonance Imaging
RPD	: Rapid progressive dementia
SWS	: Sleep wake syndrome
CJD	: Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease
GSS	: Grestmann straussler syndrome
DWI	: Diffusion Weighted Imaging
GHB	: Gamma-hydroxyburate
GH	: Growth hormone

REFERENCES

1. Khan Z, Bollu PC. Fatal Familial Insomnia. In: StatPearls [Internet]. 2021 May 10. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2021 Jan-. PMID: 29489284.
2. Smith, Yolanda. Function of Sleep. (2021, March 31). News-Medical.
3. Geschwind MD. Prion Diseases. Continuum (Minneapolis, Minn), (Neuroinfectious disease) 2015 Dec 21;16(12):38
4. Burchell JT and Panegyres PK. Prion diseases: immunotargets and therapy.
5. Lindsley CW. Genetic and rare disease of the CNS. Part I: fatal familial insomnia (FFI). ACS Chem Neurosci. 2017; 8:2570-2572.
6. Saa P, Harris DA, Cervenakova L. Mechanisms of prion-induced neurodegeneration. Expert Rev Mol Med. 2016;18: e5.
7. Medori R, Tritschler HJ, LeBlanc A, Villare F, Manetto V, Chen HY, et al. Fatal familial insomnia, a prion disease with a mutation at codon 178 of the prion protein gene. N Engl J Med. 1992; 326:444-9. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199202133260704.
8. Forloni G, Tettamanti M, Lucca U, et al. Preventive study in subjects at risk of fatal familial insomnia: innovative approach to rare diseases. Prion. 2015; 9:75-79.
9. Schenkein J, Montagna P. Self management of fatal familial insomnia. Part 1: what is FFI? MedGenMed. 2006;8(3):65. Published 2006 Sep 14.
10. Krasnianski, A., Sanchez Juan, P., Ponto, C., Bartl, M., Heinemann, U., Varges, D., Schulz-Schaeffer, W. J., Kretzschmar, H. A., & Zerr, I. (2014). A proposal of new diagnostic pathway for fatal familial insomnia. Journal of neurology, neurosurgery, and psychiatry, 85(6), 654-659.
11. Sitammagari KK, Masood W. Creutzfeldt Jakob Disease. [Updated 2021 Mar 6]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2021 Jan.
12. Liberski, P. P., Gajos, A., Sikorska, B., & Lindenbaum, S. (2019). Kuru, the First Human Prion Disease. Viruses, 11(3), 232.
13. Zhao, M. M., Feng, L. S., Hou, S., Shen, P. P., Cui, L., & Feng, J. C. (2019). Gerstmann-Sträussler-Scheinker disease: A case report. World journal of clinical cases, 7(3), 389-395.
14. Harder A, Gregor A, Wirth T, Kreuz F, Schulz-Schaeffer WJ, Windl O, Plotkin M, Amthauer H, Neukirch K, Kretzschmar HA. Early age of onset in fatal familial insomnia. Two novel cases and review of the literature. J Neurol. 2004; 251:715-724.

54878478451210704

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

